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Analysis of piston microstructure in the most critical zones

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Abstract

This paper presents the results of testing the microstructure in the most critical zones of pistons made of aluminum piston alloys. The paper analyzes the shape, size and distribution of primary Si crystals and other phases in three most important piston zones (the edge of the combustion chamber, the area of rings groove and piston pin boss). The phase stoichiometry was identified by comparing the results of EDS analysis with the results reported in the studied literature. The results show that the necessary size, shape and distribution may be obtained in specific zones if appropriate solidification conditions are provided that are necessary for the formation of specific phases.

Key words: piston, piston alloy, microstructure

1. Introduction

Piston alloys are a special group of industrial aluminum alloys that have good mechanical properties at elevated temperatures (approximately up to 350 °C) [1], and are resistant to sudden temperature changes [1]. During exploitation, these alloys are exposed to the aggressiveness of the environment in which they are used [1]. Typical aluminum piston alloys are very complex with respect to their chemical composition and the obtained structures. Different piston alloys have various contents of major and minor alloying elements. The usual ranges for some of the alloying elements used by the well-known manufacturers of pistons KS Kolbenschmidt GmbH and MAHLE GmbH from Germany and the local Concern PDM Mladenovac, Serbia are: 11–23 wt.% Si; 0.5–3 wt.% Ni; 0.5–5.5 wt.% Cu; 0.6–1.3 wt.% Mg; up to 1.0 wt.% Fe and up to 1 wt.% Mn [1–4].

Piston alloy microstructure can be very different. It is not accidental but rather affected by the strictly defined rules. The microstructure is caused, on the one hand, by the chemical composition of the alloy and solidification method and, on the other hand, by heat treatment. In the piston alloys, there are at least six elements (Al, Si, Cu, Ni, Mg and Fe), which have a

significant impact on the solidification path of these alloys. Interactions among them create different phases and intermetallics, the shape and distribution of which in the as-cast and heat-treated alloys depend on the corresponding process parameters. Al-Si piston alloys have a different structure depending on the content of silicon and other alloying elements. The results of previous tests show dependence between the combination of alloying elements, casting conditions and heat treatment given to different microstructures [1–5]. The structural composition of the material has a direct impact on the physical and mechanical properties of the casting.

Taking into account that the Si crystals are a primary phase in eutectic and hyper eutectic piston alloys, the sequence of solidification is: $L \rightarrow (Si)$, $L \rightarrow (Al) + (Si)$, $L \rightarrow (Al) + (Si) + Y$ and $L + Y \rightarrow (Al) + (Si) + Y$, where Y is: (ϵ -Al₃Ni, θ -Al₂Cu, M-Mg₂Si, δ -Al₃CuNi(Al₃Ni₂), γ -Al₇Cu₄Ni, T-Al₉FeSi, β -Al₅FeSi, π -Al₈FeMg₃Si₆ and Q-Al₅Cu₂Mg₈Si₆) [1–5], while primary aluminum phase also appears in the microstructure in hypo eutectic alloys. Based on the previous studies of all authors, it has been shown that only these phases may be present in the casting made of Al-Si piston alloys.

Based on the data from the literature, microhard-

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